

The Effect of Supply Chain Management on Competitive Advantage and Its Impact on the Operational Performance of Mobile Counter in Ambon City

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Abstract: Business competition between companies is increasingly fierce encouraging companies to produce the best performance. Companies must be able to create competitive advantage in order to produce economic value for the company better than competitors. This study aims to analyze the effect of supply chain management on competitive advantage and its impact on company performance. The research sample used in this study were 34 owners of Mobile and Credit Counter in Ambon City. The analysis technique used is Partial Least Square (PLS).

Data from data analysis shows that supply chain management construct has a positive beta value of 0.794 and significant 0.000, this proves that supply chain management has a positive and significant effect on competitive advantage. The supply chain management construct also has a positive beta value of 0.652 and a significance of 0.000, this also proves that supply chain management has a positive and significant effect on company performance. The results also found that the construct of competitive advantage has a positive beta value of 0.327 and a significance of 0.004, this indicates that competitive advantage has a significant effect on firm performance.

Keywords: supply chain management, competitive advantage and company performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The progress of science and technology is currently developing very rapidly. In the business world things like this become a challenge so that companies continue to spur their efforts to always increase production results and achieve high sales. Companies are required to keep abreast of developments by always doing innovation, efficiency, and fast service in order to stay ahead in the market. In the face of these conditions the company needs a strategy advantage to compete in order to remain viable. According to (Porter, 1993) with the existence of a competitive advantage strategy within the company, it is expected that the organization can maintain its competitive position against competitors. Business competition between companies is increasingly fierce encouraging companies to produce the best performance. companies must be able to create competitive advantage in order to produce economic value for the company better than competitors (Barney, J. B., & William, 2008). Companies need to implement supply chain management optimally. The implementation of supply chain management is able to reduce the effects of competition in the market because supply chain management can produce a competitive advantage of the company.

Companies can achieve competitive advantage by carrying out supply chain management optimally and well. The company produces better performance than competitors because supply chain management is able to minimize overall costs to understand and serve the needs of consumers. Supply chain management is all parties involved, both directly and indirectly in fulfilling customer orders and demands (Chopra, S dan Meindl, 2011). All parties involved do not only consist of producers or suppliers, they also involve distributors, storage areas, sellers and consumers.

According to (Kotler, 2010) competitive advantage is an advantage over competitors obtained by offering lower value or by providing great benefits because of higher prices to achieve maximum and sustainable competitive advantage, companies must continue to assess results which has been achieved in its vision and mission. The competitive advantage is obtained by the company through the level of product quality, service and price that meets the tastes and demands of consumers where the company is able to maintain its superiority among competitors who are increasing. In addition to the company having a competitive advantage that aims to win competition in the business

The Effect of Supply Chain Management on Competitive Advantage and Its Impact on The Operational Performance of Mobile Counter in Ambon City

environment, the company also uses competitive advantage as a way to achieve the desired company performance (R. dan D. Suharto, 2013).

According to (Pramana, 2014) in an effort to obtain a competitive advantage one of which can be done by focusing on suppressing the cost of producing goods so that at the lowest cost point but still able to meet customer needs that can be done by implementing supply chain management for the company. Supply chain management is an approach to streamline the integration of suppliers or suppliers, manufactures, warehouse storage of goods, so that goods are produced and distributed in the right amount, the right time, to minimize costs incurred and provide service satisfaction to the final consumer (David Simchi-Levi, 2000). Through the supply chain, a company is able to build long-term competitive advantage in order to continue to be competitive in a tight business environment. Well-integrated supply chain management such as the right supply of goods to continuously improve competitiveness that has an impact on company performance, the Company continues to plan strategies so that it can dominate the expected market in accordance with planned targets. By planning an optimal supply chain strategy, it can produce good performance.

The implementation of supply chain management is very necessary for companies to improve industrial competitiveness that has an impact on company performance. The company needs to consider supply chain issues to ensure that supply chain management supports the strategy of the company (Heizer Jay, 2017). The company's strategy is used in operational development in order to be able to compete and master the positions in the market. Competitive advantage strategy in the company is expected to be able to maintain the position of its competitors in the face of competitors and can improve company performance in accordance with the target.

The strict development of information technology, communication and manufacturing processes has resulted in shortened product life cycles. Therefore, every company will make every effort to increase productivity, efficiency, service that is fast, easy, and continue to create new innovations to stay ahead and survive in the market. If the company wants to at least survive in business competition, then the company must achieve these advantages, by producing good performance, the company is required to provide appropriate strategic planning. This must be immediately realized because the development of increasingly innovative and varied technologies has made the development of retail and SME companies increasingly declining.

The relationship between suppliers and producers must be healthy and maintained, because the level of dependence of companies on suppliers (suppliers) is very high and long-term, because both large companies and small companies always carry out logistics activities. For this reason, it is necessary to have a properly integrated supply chain so that it can increase the competitive advantage of the product.

This study aims to analyze the effect of supply chain management on competitive advantage and its impact on company performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Supply Chain Management

Supply chain management is the integration of materials and service procurement activities, conversion into semi-finished goods and final products, and delivery to customers (Heizer Jay, 2017). (David Simchi-Levi, 2000) states supply chain management as an approach applied to bring together suppliers, entrepreneurs, warehouses, and other storage areas (distributors, retailers, and retailers) efficiently, so that products can be produced and distributed in the right amount, the right location, and the right time to lower costs and meet customer needs.

(Indrajit, R. E., Djokopranoto, 2010) revealed that supply chain management is a system where the organization distributes production goods and services to its customers, the supply chain is also a network of several interconnected organizations and has the same goal, namely the best possible procurement of goods, the term supply Chain management also includes the process of changing the goods. The purpose of supply chain management is to maximize the overall value generated to meet customer needs and demands with the other goal is to minimize overall costs (ordering costs, storage costs, raw material costs, transportation costs, etc. (R. Suharto & Devie, 2013).

Competitive Advantage

Today it is increasingly believed that the main key in winning competition is to provide value and satisfaction to customers through the delivery of quality products and services at competitive prices (Fandy Tjiptono, 2012). According to (Kotler, 2010), to win the current market, companies must be skilled not only in managing products, but also in managing relationships with customers to face competition. Building a profitable customer relationship and achieving competitive advantage requires delivering more value and satisfaction to the customer than is done with competitors. The offer is also with competitive advantage, where the company has an advantage over competitors obtained by offering greater value to consumers than competitors' offers. Companies need to understand competitors and customers through analysis to achieve competitive advantage.

The Effect of Supply Chain Management on Competitive Advantage and Its Impact on The Operational Performance of Mobile Counter in Ambon City

Companies that have competitive advantages have the ability to understand market changes and are able to choose effective strategies. Competitive advantage is the ability of a company to achieve economic benefits over the profits achieved by the same competitor or the same industry. According to (Li, Suhong, Bhanu Ragu-Nathanb, T.S. Ragu Nathanb, 2006) competitive advantage is the extent to which a company is able to create a position that can be maintained over its competitors. It consists of abilities that enable an organization to differentiate itself from competitors.

Competitive advantage is the company's ability to meet customer needs effectively and efficiently with products or services that have more value or at a lower cost (Porter, 1993). The ability of a company to achieve economic benefits above the profit that can be achieved by competitors in the market in the same industry. Companies that have a competitive advantage always have the ability to understand changes in market structure and are able to choose effective marketing strategies. The choice of each company for the above strategy will depend on the analysis of the business environment to determine opportunities and threats. Based on studies conducted by Porter, several ways to gain competitive advantage include offering products or services at a minimum price, offering products or services that are unique to their competitors, or focusing on specific segments (Goyal, S.K. and Giri, 2001).

Company performance

Company performance is something that is produced by a company in a certain period with reference to the standards set (Rahmasari, 2011). (Rahadi, 2010) explains that company performance is something that is produced by a company within a certain period by referring to predetermined standards. Company performance is the result that can be measured and determined by showing the empirical condition of the company of various specified sizes. Business performance refers to how much the market-oriented company and profit goals.

Company performance can be measured based on certain standards or indicators, company performance includes the level of productivity, the level of product error, guarantee or warranty costs, quality costs and the level of product storage in the hands of consumers on time. To achieve this, there needs to be a good appraisal performance system, including: (1) organizational activities and emphasizing the improvement of consumer perspectives, (2) assessing each activity using customer-oriented performance measurement tools (3) considering all aspects of performance as a whole that can influence consumers (4) provide information feedback to help all members of the organization to recognize problems and opportunities to be able to make improvements continuously (Rahadi, 2010).

Performance is the success of personnel, teams, or organizational units in realizing the pre-determined strategic goals with expected behavior. Performance is the result or overall level of success of a person during a certain period in carrying out the task compared with various possibilities, such as the standard work results, targets or targets.

Performance can be defined as the final result with all activities carried out by the company which are adjusted to the established criteria. Performance also reflects the achievements achieved by an organization. The short term goal of supply chain management is to reduce inventory, cycle time and productivity. The long-term goal of supply chain management is to increase sales and profits.

Relationship Between Supply Chain Management and Competitive Advantage

Supply chain management has an influence on competitive advantage where supply chain management indicators include supplier partnership strategies, customer relations, and information sharing so that it affects competitive advantage with indicators of price, quality, product innovation, delivery dependability and time to market. Where the implementation of a good supply chain can increase the company's competitive advantage (R. Suharto & Devie, 2013). (Rahmasari, 2011) in her research concluded that effective supply chain management has a positive and significant effect on competitive advantage, effective supply chain management is influenced by the development of supplier relations strategies, planning and control, production and distribution, information quality and purchasing.

Research by (Li, Suhong, Bhanu Ragu-Nathanb, T.S. Ragu Nathanb, 2006) states that effective supply chain management has the potential to increase competitive advantage. Evidenced by integrated supply chain management starting from the relationship to suppliers and customers, delays and quality are able to maintain and strengthen their competitiveness in winning competition in the market.

A good supply chain management in a company will give a competitive advantage to the company. The principle of supply chain management is to do the competition itself controlled by the company and give a part that is not a company's competence in other parts of the supply chain. This will make the supply chain effective. In this case, supply chain management will influence the goods distributed to outlets but to goods that are the needs of the final consumer. With effective supply chain management, the supply of goods to consumers will be fulfilled by taking into account the value that is important to consumers (high sales and low inventory levels) and serving consumers with

The Effect of Supply Chain Management on Competitive Advantage and Its Impact on The Operational Performance of Mobile Counter in Ambon City

good service and products. This is an indicator of increasing competitive advantage. From the description above it can be drawn a hypothesis:

H1: Supply chain management has a positive effect on competitive advantage

Relationship Between Supply Chain Management and Company Performance

Supply chain management has an influence on company performance (Karimi, Ebrahim, 2014). Where the indicators that include supply chain management play an important role and influence on company performance. Supply chain management influences company performance even though with different indicators namely material, financial, and information. Implementation of a good supply chain will be able to improve company performance.

Previous research identified that various dimensions in supply chain management such as supplier strategy partnerships, information quality, and customer relations have an influence on several aspects of company performance. Effective and optimal supply chain management can increase productivity, market share and customer growth (Rahmasari, 2011). Research by (Li, Suhong, Bhanu Ragu-Nathanb, T.S. Ragu Nathanb, 2006) states that effective supply chain management has the potential to improve company performance by using four dimensions of its supply chain, namely: supplier relationships, customer relationships, level of information sharing, and postponement.

The implementation of good supply chain management will be able to improve company performance. Research on companies in Surabaya shows that many companies pay little attention to aspects of supply chain management in terms of strategic partnerships for periodic continuous improvement with suppliers so that the quality produced by suppliers affects the company in its performance both in production and sales (R. Suharto & Devie, 2013) .

The conceptual model of the supply chain to be developed in this study shows that supply chain management has a direct impact on firm performance. Supply chain management has three objectives, namely cost reduction, capital reduction, and service improvement. Of the three objectives, the purpose of cost reduction means that by implementing supply chain management, companies can reduce logistics costs incurred, for example by choosing transportation equipment or models, distribution systems, warehousing, standards and services that minimize costs. Likewise with the goal of capital reduction, the implementation of supply chain management is expected to improve company performance by increasing the rate of return on capital.

On the side of the company's operations, supply chain management will help companies to produce and distribute goods in the right amount, location and time. With these provisions will certainly have an impact on increasing sales, profits, and market share which are indicators of company performance. From the above statement it can be concluded that supply chain management will be able to improve company performance. From the description above it can be drawn a hypothesis:

H2: Supply chain management has a positive effect on company performance

Relationship Between Excellence Competing With Company Performance

Competitive advantage affects company performance, competitive advantage is measured by indicators of price, quality, product innovation, delivery dependability, and time to market (Pramana, 2014). In addition to having a competitive advantage that aims to win the competition, the company also uses competitive advantage as a way to achieve the desired company performance goals (R. dan D. Suharto, 2013).

(Rahmasari, 2011) research concluded that competitive advantage had a positive and significant effect on company performance. Lower prices, high quality, speed of delivery and continuous product innovation are proven to increase product sales and dominate market share. Product sales and market share mastery are the benchmarks in a company achieving market-oriented corporate performance and financial goals.

Competitive advantage develops from the value that companies can create for customers or buyers using competitive dimensions, advantages, which consist of price, quality, delivery dependability, time to market and product innovation (Li, Suhong, Bhanu Ragu-Nathanb, T.S. Ragu Nathanb, 2006). From the description above, we can draw a hypothesis:

H3: Competitive advantage has a positive effect on company performance

To facilitate a research, it is necessary to make a research framework that describes a relationship of the influence of supply chain management on company performance in accordance with hypotheses and literature reviews, then the following theoretical framework is prepared:

Figure 2. Research Model

III. RESEARCH METHODS

Types of research

This research is a survey study using an instrument designed in the form of a questionnaire to obtain primary data from the mobile counter in Ambon City. This study was also designed to test hypotheses with the aim of uncovering the influence of supply chain management variables on competitive advantage and their impact on operational performance.

Population and Sample

According to (Sugiyono, 2017), population is related to the whole group of people, events, or objects that are the center of attention of researchers to be examined. The population that is the object of this research is the mobile counter in Ambon City. The research sample used in this study were 34 owners of mobile counter in Ambon City.

Endogenous Constructions

Supply Chain Management

Supply chain management is the integration of materials and service procurement activities, conversion into semi-finished goods and final products, and delivery to customers (Heizer Jay, 2017).

Exogenous Constructions

Competitive Advantage

Competitive advantage is the company's ability to meet customer needs effectively and efficiently with products or services that have more value or at a lower cost (Porter, 1993).

Company Performance

Company performance is something that is produced by a company in a certain period with reference to the standards set (Rahmasari, 2011).

Data Analysis Techniques

Partial Least Square (PLS) was first developed by (Wold, 1975). PLS is a powerful analytical model because it can be used on any type of data scale (nominal, ordinal, interval and ratio) as well as more flexible assumption requirements. PLS can also be regarded as a PLS approach to structural equation modeling. In the PLS community, the term "path modeling" is preferred over structural Equation Modeling. Nevertheless, these two terms can be found in the PLS literature.

PLS does not assume the data must follow a certain distribution, for example normal distribution. The PLS approach is a free distribution and flexible sample size. PLS can also be used when the theoretical basis of the model is tentative or the measurement of each latent construct is still new (Yamin, 2011). Variant-based PLS that was designed with the aim of prediction. This is an initial concept that should be the basis for researchers. The main focus of PLS is to maximize endogenous construct variants that can be explained by exogenous constructs or identify constructs to be able to maximize the predictive power of the model. Mentions PLS can also be for confirmation purposes (such as hypothesis testing) and exploration purposes. The main purpose is to explain the relationship between constructs and emphasize the understanding of the value of the relationship.

To facilitate the research, the data processing in this study uses the XLSTAT PLS-PM 2014 software.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Quality Test Results

Validity test is done by using an evaluation of measurement model (outer) by using convergent validity. Convergent validity of the measurement model with reflexive indicators can be from the correlation between each construct score (Ghozali, 2016). The individual reflexive measure is said to be high if the correlation is more than (0.70) with the construct to be measured, but according to (Chin, 1998) for research in the early stages of developing the scale of measurement of values (0.5) to (0.6) is considered sufficient. The results of the validity test using convergent validity values calculated with PLS can be seen in table 1.

Table 1, Convergent Validity Results

	Supply Chain Management	Competitive Advantage	Company Performance
SCM1	0,871	0,611	0,776
SCM2	0,698	0,382	0,560
SCM3	0,850	0,617	0,814
SCM4	0,858	0,519	0,743
SCM5	0,860	0,638	0,843
SCM6	0,889	0,648	0,784
SCM7	0,917	0,738	0,882
SCM8	0,739	0,470	0,639
SCM9	0,865	0,848	0,759
SCM10	0,725	0,913	0,753
CA1	0,869	0,790	0,854
CA2	0,263	0,600	0,190
CA3	0,327	0,728	0,346
CA4	0,721	0,849	0,614
CA5	0,577	0,861	0,458
CA6	0,533	0,880	0,568
CA7	0,719	0,780	0,840
CA8	0,761	0,899	0,776
CA9	0,455	0,858	0,579
CA10	0,704	0,795	0,879
CP1	0,716	0,632	0,829
CP2	0,688	0,602	0,804
CP3	0,878	0,739	0,928
CP4	0,863	0,802	0,947
CP5	0,897	0,841	0,950
CP6	0,878	0,711	0,886
CP7	0,886	0,804	0,932
CP8	0,892	0,858	0,974
CP9	0,876	0,851	0,946
CP10	0,834	0,845	0,958

Source: Primary data, processed 2020

Indicators SCM 1 through SCM 10 that are used to measure supply chain management constructs have a high correlation above the number (0.500), this shows that statements about supply chain management to measure supply chain management constructs are declared valid. CA indicators 1 to CA 10 which are used to measure the construct of Competitive Advantage have a high correlation above the number (0.500), this shows that the statement of competitive advantage to measure the construct of competitive advantage is declared valid. CP indicators 1 through CP 10 which are used to measure the construct of Company performance have a high correlation above the number (0.500), this shows that the statement about the company's performance to measure the construct of the company's performance is valid.

The next examination of the discriminant validity evaluation is comparing the AVE value of each construct with the square of the correlation between constructs.

Table 2. Results of Discriminant Validity

	Supply Chain Management	Competitive Advantage	Company Performance	Mean Communalities (AVE)
Supply chain management	1	0,630	0,830	0,689
Competitive Advantage	0,630	1	0,713	0,653
Company Performance	0,830	0,713	1	0,841
Mean Communalities (AVE)	0,689	0,653	0,841	0

Source: Primary data, processed 2020

The AVE value for supply chain management constructs is (0.089) while the square of correlation of supply chain management constructs with other constructs (the first row in the table) is smaller than the AVE value of constructs. The AVE value for the construct of competitive advantage is (0.563) while the square of the correlation of constructs of competitive advantage with other constructs (the second row in the table) is smaller than the value of AVE constructs. The AVE value for constructs of firm performance is (0.841) while the square of correlation of constructs of firm performance with other constructs (third row in the table) is smaller than the value of AVE constructs. These results indicate that the constructs in this study have good discriminant validity.

Then the reliability test is performed by looking at the composite reliability values generated by calculating the PLS for each construct. The value of a construct is said to be reliable if it gives a composite reliability value > 0.80 (Werst, et.al 1974 in (Ghozali, 2016)). The reliability test results are presented in table 3.

Table 3. Reliability Test Results

Latent variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Supply chain management	0,949	0,957
Competitive Advantage	0,943	0,952
Company Performance	0,979	0,981

Source: Primary data, processed 2020

The supply chain management construct has a composite reliability value (0.957) as mentioned above (0.80) as a cutoff value, then all questions about supply chain management are reliable. While the competitive advantage construct has a composite reliability value (0.952) the value mentioned above (0.80) as a cutoff value, then all questions about competitive advantage are reliable. Furthermore, the construct of company performance has a composite reliability value (0.981), the value mentioned above (0.80) as a cutoff value, thus all questions about company performance are reliable.

Assessment of the model with PLS starts with looking at the R-square for each dependent latent construct. Changes in the value of R-square can be used to assess the effect of certain independent latent constructs on the dependent latent construct whether it has a substantive effect. The following table is the result of R-square estimation using XLSTAT PLS PM.

Table 4. R Square Value (R2) (Company Performance)

R ²	F	Pr > F
0,630	54,545	0,000

Source: Primary data, processed 2020

Table 4 above shows the R² value of the construct of company performance is 0.630. The higher the value of R², the greater the independent construct can explain the dependent construct, so the better the structural equation. R² value of the company's performance construct is 0.630 which means that 63% of the variance of company performance is explained by supply chain management, competitive advantage, and company performance while the remaining 37% is explained by other constructs outside this study.

Hypothesis 1

The first hypothesis (H1) states that supply chain management has a positive effect on competitive advantage. Table 5 below shows that supply chain management has a positive effect on competitive advantage. The influence of supply chain management construct on positive competitive advantage (0.794) and significant at (7.385 > 1.96), then hypothesis 1 is accepted.

Table 5. Inner Weights Results

Latent variable	Value	T	Pr> t	Hypothesis
Supply chain management	0,794	7,385	0.000	Received

Source: Primary data, processed 2020

Hypothesis 2

The second hypothesis (H2) states that supply chain management has a positive effect on company performance. Table 6 below shows that supply chain management has a positive effect on company performance. The effect of supply chain management construct on firm performance is positive (0.652) and significant at (6.105 > 1.96), so hypothesis 2 is accepted.

Table 6. Inner Weights Results (Company Performance)

Latent variable	Value	T	Pr> t	Hypothesis
Supply chain management	0,652	6,105	0.000	Received

Source: Primary data, processed 2020

Hypothesis 3

The third hypothesis (H3) states that competitive advantage has a positive effect on company performance. Table 7 below shows that competitive advantage has a positive effect on company performance. The effect of the construct of competitive advantage on positive company performance (0.327) and significant at (3.067 > 1.96), then hypothesis 3 is accepted.

Table 7. Inner Weights Results (Company Performance)

Latent variable	Value	T	Pr> t	Hypothesis
Competitive advantage	0,327	3,067	0.004	Received

Source: Primary data, processed 2020

Full Model

Figure 2. Full Model.

Discussion

Based on the results of using Partial Least Square above shows that supply chain management has a positive and significant effect on competitive advantage, and supply chain management also has a positive and significant effect on company performance, the results of this study also show that competitive advantage has a positive and significant effect on company performance.

The Effect of Supply Chain Management on Competitive Advantage and Its Impact on The Operational Performance of Mobile Counter in Ambon City

Data from data analysis shows that supply chain management construct has a positive beta value of 0.794 and significant 0.000, this proves that supply chain management has a positive and significant effect on competitive advantage. The supply chain management construct also has a positive beta value of 0.652 and a significance of 0.000, this also proves that supply chain management has a positive and significant effect on company performance. The results also found that the construct of competitive advantage has a positive beta value of 0.327 and a significance of 0.004, this indicates that competitive advantage has a significant effect on firm performance.

The results of this study prove that supply chain management influences excellence. The supply chain management construct has a positive beta value of 0.794 and a significant 0.000, this shows that supply chain management has a positive and significant effect on competitive advantage. The results of this study support previous research conducted by (Li, Suhong, Bhanu Ragu-Nathanb, T.S. Ragu Nathanb, 2006) stating that there is a significant influence between supply chain management on competitive advantage so it is the same as the research conducted now.

The results of this study also prove that supply chain management influences company performance. The supply chain management construct has a positive beta value of 0.652 and a significant 0.000, this shows that supply chain management has a positive and significant effect on company performance. The results of this study support previous research conducted by (Karimi, Ebrahim, 2014) which states that supply chain management has a positive influence on company performance. This study also supports research conducted by (R. dan D. Suharto, 2013) stating that supply chain management has a significant influence on company performance and the implementation of good supply chain management will be able to improve company performance both operational and financial performance.

The results of this study also prove that competitive advantage affects company performance. The construct of competitive advantage has a positive beta value of 0.327 and a significance of 0.004, this shows that competitive advantage has a positive and significant effect on company performance. The results of this study support previous research conducted by (Pramana, 2014) stating that competitive advantage has a significant effect on company performance. As well as supporting research conducted by (R. dan D. Suharto, 2013) states that competitive advantage has a significant effect on company performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The test results using Partial Least Square, it can be concluded that:

- 1) Supply chain management has a positive effect on competitive advantage. This is indicated by the influence of the SCM construct on positive competitive advantage (0.794) and is significant at (7.385 > 1.96). For that every company must maintain a good competitive advantage. The results support the research conducted by (Rahmasari, 2011), (Li, Suhong, Bhanu Ragu-Nathanb, T.S. Ragu Nathanb, 2006).
- 2) Supply chain management has a positive effect on company performance. This is indicated by the influence of the SCM contract on positive company performance (0.652) and significant at (6.105 > 1.96). For this reason, cellphone and pulse counter companies in Ambon city must always use the SCM approach so that the company's performance remains good. The results support the study conducted by (Karimi, Ebrahim, 2014).
- 3) Competitive advantage influences company performance. This is indicated by the influence of competitive advantage on positive company performance (0.327) and significant (3.067 > 1.96), so it is declared acceptable so there is an effect of competitive advantage on company performance.

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The Effect of Supply Chain Management on Competitive Advantage and Its Impact on The Operational Performance of Mobile Counter in Ambon City

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